

4-Thiazolidinones as Potential Antibacterial and Antitubercular Agents

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2-Aryl-3-[3-(4-methyl/methoxyphenyl)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione-5-yl]-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared from the reaction of thioglycolic acid with azomethines in dry benzene. The azomethines have been prepared by condensation of different aromatic aldehyde with 5-amino-3-(4-methyl/methoxyphenyl)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione. 4-Thiazolidinones show antibacterial activity when tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by nutrient agar pour plate method, and have been tested against $H_{37}R_0$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

THIAZOLIDINONES belong to an important group of heterocyclic compounds, having carbonyl group at position 2, 4 or 5 is the subject of extensive study. Several substituted thiazolidinones, biologically active compounds were prepared^{1,2} and found to have anaesthetic, anticonvulsant and sedative properties. Besides, these compounds having =N-C-S- grouping have antitubercular, hematocidal, anticonvulsant, herbicidal, antifungal, insecticidal, hypnotic, anthelmintic, cardiovascular and antibacterial properties³⁻¹³. We have prepared 2-aryl-3-[3-(4-methyl/methoxyphenyl)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione-5-yl]-4-thiazolidinones. 5-Amino-3-(4-methyl/methoxyphenyl)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione have been prepared by the reported method¹⁴. Elemental analysis was carried out on semi-micro C, H, N analyser. The ir spectra (KBr) were taken on Perkin-Elmer 137 G spectrometer.

Experimental

Preparation of Schiff bases : 5-Amino-3-(4-methyl/methoxyphenyl)-thiazolidine-2,4-dione (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml, 95%) and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) added and refluxed on water-bath for 3 h. The product was distilled until Schiff base commenced to crystallise (Table 1).

Preparation of 4-thiazolidinones : To the Schiff base (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 ml) was added thioglycolic acid and the contents refluxed for 8 h until water collected in Dean and Stark trap. Excess of benzene was removed, treated with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 and extracted with ether. The ether extract was treated with dried Na_2SO_4 , ether distilled off. The residue on crystallisation gave thiazolidinone (Table 2).

Pharmacological screening : 4-Thiazolidinones were screened for antituberculostatic and antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Table 2).

TABLE 1—SCHIFF BASE COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Analysis % (Found)/(Calcd.)
N				
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃	158	8.92 (9.03)
2.	-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	„	132	8.21 (8.58)
3.	-5-Br-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	„	172	7.11 (6.91)
4.	-3,5-diBr-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	„	135	6.01 (5.78)
5.	-4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	„	121	9.02 (8.64)
6.	-2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	„	138	7.91 (8.12)
7.	-4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	„	191	11.93 (11.79)
8.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	„	164	11.96 (11.79)
9.	-3-OCH ₃ -4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	„	172	7.52 (7.86)
10.	-C ₆ H ₅	-OCH ₃	131	8.69 (8.58)
11.	-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	„	122	8.14 (7.82)
12.	-4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	„	139	7.52 (7.86)
13.	-4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	„	152	8.02 (7.79)
14.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	„	128	10.55 (10.82)
15.	-3,5-diBr-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	„	170	5.52 (5.38)

In vitro antitubercular activity of the hitherto synthesised hydrazones and 4-thiazolidinones was studied against $H_{37}R_0$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at $0.02 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The retardation of the growth rate has been studied upto six weeks at 37° .

TABLE 2 — 4-THIAZOLIDINONES

Sl. no.	R	R'	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	M. p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.) N	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i> <i>E. coli</i>	<i>M. tuberculosis</i> * H ₃₇ R _v	
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃		140	7.56 (7.29)	-	-	+
2.	-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"	3588 (OH) 1730 (C=O) 1220 (4 TR)	170	6.89 (7.00)	+	-	+
3.	-5-Br-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"		132	6.01 (5.34)	+	-	+
4.	-3,5-diBr-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"		122	5.21 (5.01)	++	+	+
5.	-4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	"		159	7.32 (7.03)	+	+	+
6.	-2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	"		183	6.84 (6.69)	-	-	+
7.	-4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	"		170	9.58 (9.97)	+	-	+
8.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	"		180	9.52 (9.97)	+	-	+
9.	-3-OCH ₃ -4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"	3595 (OH) 1742 (C=O) 1200 (4 TR)	192	6.82 (6.51)	+	+	+
10.	-C ₆ H ₅	-OCH ₃	850 (-C ₆ H ₅) 1750 (C=O) 1310 (4 TR)	154	7.32 (7.00)	-	-	+
11.	-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"	3570 (OH) 1720 (C=O) 1325 (4 TR)	134	6.53 (6.73)	+	-	+
12.	-4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	"		118	6.78 (6.51)	+	-	+
13.	-4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	"		200	6.68 (6.44)	+	+	+
14.	-3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	"		142	9.12 (9.43)	-	-	+
15.	-3,5-diBr-2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	"		190	5.03 (4.71)	++	+	+

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, S analyses.

4 TR = 4-Thiazolidinone ring system.

(+) = Zone dia. less than 20 mm.

(++) = Zone dia. more than 20 mm.

*Concentration 0.02 µg ml⁻¹.

The antibacterial activity was tested by nutrient agar pour plate method in dimethyl formamide and found to be active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* organisms in various concentrations.

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